

General Uses In Intermediate Value Theorems

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 20, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Intermediate Value Theorems, A Twice-Differentiablefunction, Lagrange Theorem, Rolle Theorem, Cauchy Theorem.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5228752</p>	<p>Let f be a real-valued and atwice-differentiablefunction in the interval(1,3), letso</p> <p>$f(1) = f(2) = f(3)$, then there is a point $c \in (1,3)$, in which $f''(c) = 0$. (This particular case is true according to [3]).The first purpose of this article is to generalize this particular case.</p> <p>Let f be a real-valued and a twice-differentiablefunction in the interval $[-1,1]$, and let</p> <p>$f(-1) + f(1) = 2f(0)$, then there is a point $c \in (-1,1)$, inwhich $f''(c) = 0$. (This particular case is true according to [4]). The second purpose of this article is to generalize this particular case too.</p> <p>Let f be a real-valued and a continuous functionin the interval $[0,2]$, and let $f(0) = f(2)$, and</p> <p>$f(0) < f(1)$, then there is a point $c \in (0,1)$such that $f(c) = f(c + 1)$. (This particular case is true according to [2]). The third purpose of this article is to generalize this particular case too.</p>

Introduction

We will need the following Intermediate value theorems:

Cauchy theorem:Let f be a continuous real-valued function in a closed interval $[a, b]$, and Let y_0 be a real number between $f(a)$ and $f(b)$, ($f(a) \leq y_0 \leq f(b)$).

Then there is $x_0 \in [a, b]$ in which $f(x_0) = y_0$.

Rolle theorem: Let f be a continuous real-valued function in a closed interval $[a, b]$, differentiable on the open interval (a, b) and $f(a) = f(b)$, then there exists at least one $x_0 \in (a, b)$ in which: $f'(x_0) = 0$.

Lagrange's Mean Value Theorem: Let f be a real-valued function defined on the closed interval $[a, b]$. If f satisfies the two following conditions, f is continuous on the closed interval $[a, b]$, and f is differentiable on the open interval (a, b) .

Then there exists a value $x = x_0$ in which $f'(x_0) = \frac{f(b)-f(a)}{b-a}$.

New result:

Our main result presented in the following lemmas:

Lemma 1:

If f a real-valued and a twice differentiablefunction in the interval (α, γ) , and if there is $\beta \in (\alpha, \gamma)$ which satisfies $f(\alpha) = f(\beta) = f(\gamma)$, then there is a point $x_0 \in (\alpha, \gamma)$, in which $f''(x_0) = 0$.

Lemma2:

If f is a real-valued and a twice-differentiablefunction in the interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, and if

$$f(\alpha) + f(\beta) = 2f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right).$$

Then there is a point $\gamma \in (\alpha, \beta)$, which satisfies $f''(\gamma) = 0$.

Lemma 3:

If f is a real-valued and a continuous function in the interval $[0, \alpha]$, $\alpha \geq 2$ and f satisfying the two following conditions:

1. $f(0) = f(\alpha)$.
2. $f(0) < f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)$.

Then there is a point $\beta \in (0, \frac{\alpha}{2})$ in which $f(\beta) = f(\beta + 1)$.

Proof Lemma 1:

Let f be a real-valued and a twice-differentiablefunction in the interval $[\alpha, \gamma]$.

Suppose that $f(\alpha) = f(\beta) = f(\gamma)$ for $\beta \in (\alpha, \gamma)$

First, since that, f is a twice differentiable function in the interval $[\alpha, \gamma]$, so f and f' are differentiable functions in the interval $[\alpha, \gamma]$, and this will lead that f and f' are continuous functions in these interval, or in any part of it. (Each differentiable function is necessarily continuous).

Let us look at the interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, it is clear that f is continuous on the closed interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, and f is differentiable on the open interval (α, β) , in addition, given that, $f(\alpha) = f(\beta)$ then from Rolle's theorem, there is a point $x_1 \in (\alpha, \beta)$ in which $f'(x_1) = 0$.

In a similar way, let us look at the interval $[\beta, \gamma]$, it is clear that f is continuous on the closed interval $[\beta, \gamma]$, and f is differentiable on the open interval (β, γ) , in addition, given that,

$f(\alpha) = f(\beta)$, then from Rolle's Theorem, there is a point $x_2 \in (\beta, \gamma)$ in which $f'(x_2) = 0$.

We got that $f'(x_1) = 0$ and $f'(x_2) = 0$, in particular $f'(x_1) = f'(x_2)$, ($\alpha < x_1 < x_2 < \gamma$).

Now Since that f is a twice-differentiable function in the interval $[\alpha, \gamma]$ then f' is differentiable and continuous function in this interval, in particular if we look at f' in the interval $[x_1, x_2]$, then from Rolle's Theorem we'll get a point $x_0 \in (x_1, x_2)$, (and thus in (α, γ)), in which $f''(x_0) = 0$.

This complete the proof of Lemma 1.

Proof Lemma 2:

Let f a real-valued and a twice-differentiable function in the interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, and let f satisfy the condition $f(\alpha) + f(\beta) = 2f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right)$.

As in proof Lemma 1, also here since that, f is a twice differentiable function in the interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, so f and f' are differentiable functions in the interval $[\alpha, \beta]$, and this will lead that f and f' are continuous functions in these interval, or in any part of it.

The function f is differentiable at the interval $(\alpha, \frac{\alpha+\beta}{2})$, and continuous at the interval $[\alpha, \frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}]$, then from Lagrange's Theorem, there is a point $a \in (\alpha, \frac{\alpha+\beta}{2})$ in which

$$f'(a) = \frac{f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right) - f(\alpha)}{\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2} - \alpha} = 2 \frac{f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right) - f(\alpha)}{\beta - \alpha}$$

In addition, the function f is differentiable at the interval $(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}, \beta)$, and continuous at the interval $[\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}, \beta]$, then from Lagrange's Theorem, there is a point $b \in (\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}, \beta)$ in which

$$f'(b) = \frac{f(\beta) - f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right)}{\beta - \frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}} = 2 \frac{f(\beta) - f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right)}{\beta - \alpha}$$

From the condition

$$f(\alpha) + f(\beta) = 2f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right),$$

Then

$$f(\beta) - f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right) = f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right) - f(\alpha).$$

We will get that

$$f'(a) = 2 \frac{f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right) - f(\alpha)}{\beta - \alpha} = 2 \frac{f(\beta) - f\left(\frac{\alpha+\beta}{2}\right)}{\beta - \alpha} = f'(b)$$

Now the function f' is differentiable at the interval (a, b) , and continuous at the interval $[a, b]$, and $f'(a) = f'(b)$, then from Rolle's Theorem, there is a point $\gamma \in (a, b)$ (and thus in (α, β)) such that $f''(\gamma) = 0$.

This completes the proof of Lemma 2.

Proof Lemma 3:

Let f a real-valued and a continuous function in the interval $[0, \alpha]$, $\alpha \geq 2$ and let f satisfy the two following conditions $f(0) = f(\alpha)$, and $f(0) < f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)$.

We will define a new function g , as follows:

$$g(x) = f(x) - f\left(x + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right).$$

It is clear that g is a continuous function because it is a combination of continuous functions.

Since that $f(0) < f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)$, we will get:

$$g(0) = f(0) - f\left(0 + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) = f(0) - f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right).$$

Since that $f(0) = f(\alpha)$, we will get

$$g\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) = f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) - f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2} + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) = f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) - f(\alpha) = f\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) - f(0) > 0.$$

So based on Cauchy theorem, there is a point $\beta \in (0, \frac{\alpha}{2})$ in which $g(\beta) = 0$, this means that

$$g(\beta) = f(\beta) - f\left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right) = 0.$$

Then:

$$f(\beta) = f\left(\beta + \frac{\alpha}{2}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 1.

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